

Studies in Sulphonamides: Part IV. Some N⁶-Heterocyclic Sulphonamides from 2-Naphthylamine as possible Antibacterial Agents

R. D. Desai, G. S. Saharia* and H. S. Sodhi

Substituted thiazole, benzothiazole, pyridine and carbazole moieties have been introduced into the sulphonamido group of the sulphonamides prepared from 2-naphthylamine-6-sulphonyl chloride. All the seventeen compounds were later screened for their antibacterial activity and none of these was found to be active *in vitro* against *S. Aureus* and *E. coli*.

It has been previously shown by us¹ that some of the N¹-substituted 4-amino-1-naphthalene sulphonamides were found active *in vitro* against *S. Aureus* and *E. coli*. Prompted by these encouraging results, we have extended our investigations for the synthesis and screening of the sulphonamides prepared from 2-naphthylamine 6-sulphonyl chloride containing a heterocyclic moiety attached to nitrogen of the sulphonamido group.

The present communication describes the synthesis of seventeen N⁶-substituted 2-amino-6-naphthalene-4-sulphonamido-thiazoles, benzothiazoles, pyridines and carbazoles. These were prepared by condensing 2-acetamido-6-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride with the appropriate heterocyclic bases in equimolecular proportions, in presence of dry acetone or a mixture of dry acetone and dry pyridine when the corresponding 2-acetamido-6-naphthalene-sulphonamides were obtained; these were crystallised from ethanol, absolute ethanol or glacial acetic acid given in Table I. Subsequent hydrolysis of these with aqueous sodium hydroxide and neutralisation with dil. HCl furnished the respective N⁶-substituted 2-amino-6-naphthalene sulphonamides (Table II). A study of the antibacterial properties of these was later carried out by the cup-plate agar method^{2,3}, and as a result it was concluded that though some N¹-substituted 4-amino-1-naphthalene sulphonamides were active *in vitro* against *S. Aureus* and *S. coli*, the N⁶-substituted-2-amino-6-naphthalene sulphonamides were devoid of activity. These findings indicate the effect of the positions occupied by the groups on the activity of the compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted thiazoles⁴, benzothiazoles⁵, and carbazoles⁶ required for this work were prepared by us by the standard methods.

* To whom all correspondence should be made,

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TABLE I

*N*⁶-Substituted-2-acetamido-6-naphthalene sulphonamides (*R* = COCH₃).

Compd. No.	R'	Reaction	Time for the	*Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Yield %
		Temp. °C	reaction Hr.			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	6-Thiazolyl	70—85	5	Colourless crystals	300(d)	33.6
2.	4'-Methyl-6-thiazolyl	40—5	2	„ „	250(d)	35.1
3.	4'-Phenyl-6-thiazolyl	Room temp.	14—15	Pinkish white crystals	215	39.9
4.	4'- <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl-6-thiazolyl	„	„	Yellow needles	250	38.2
5.	4'- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-6-thiazolyl	80	5	Dark-brown crystals	235	56.5
6.	4'- <i>p</i> -Anisyl-6-thiazolyl	Room temp.	14—15	„ „	201	40.6
7.	4' : 5'-Dimethyl-6-thiazolyl	40—5	2 ×	Yellow crystals	195	44.5
8.	4'-Methyl-5'-carbethoxy-6-thiazolyl	75—80	5	Light-brown crystals	300(d)	48.6
9.	4'-Phenyl-5'-iodo-6-thiazolyl	40—50	4	Reddish orange crystals	198	30.7
10.	4' : 5'-Diiodo-6-thiazolyl	60	4	Brown crystals	239(d)	43.1
11.	6'-Methyl-6-benzo-thiazolyl	80	8	Pinkish white crystals	225	53.5
12.	6'-Methoxy-6-benzo-thiazolyl	40—5	2	Violet crystals	160	43.0
13.	6'-Chloro-6-benzo-thiazolyl	40—50	2	Colourless crystals	235	53.2
14.	6-Pyridyl	30—40	½	Pinkish white needles	235	46.8
15.	5'-Iodo-6-pyridyl	Room temp.	8	Brown coloured product	220—1	39.9
16.	6-Carbazolyl	40—50	2	Light brown crystals	230	40.4
17.	3'-(6-Carbazolyl)	40	1	Bright yellow prisms	202—3	32.6

* Crystallised from glacial acetic acid, ethanol or absolute ethanol.

'd' denotes decomposition,

TABLE II

*N*⁶-Substituted-2-amino-6-naphthalene sulphonamides (*R* = *H*).

Compd. No.*	M.P. °C	Yield %	Crystalline appearance**	Mol. formula	Carbon %		Hydrogen %		Sulphur %	
					Found	Re-quired	Found	Re-quired	Found	Re-quired
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1.	300(d)	57.0	Colourless crystals	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	51.3	51.1	3.7	3.5	21.3	21.0
2.	280	56.8	„ „	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	52.8	52.6	4.4	4.1	20.3	20.1
3.	241	79.9	Light brown needles	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	60.1	59.8	4.1	3.9	16.6	16.8
4.	110	52.7	Yellowish white needles	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	53.7	53.5	3.5	3.2	15.3	15.0
5.	195	38.7	Yellow crystals	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	54.6	54.8	3.2	3.4	15.7	15.4
6.	158	66.1	Grey crystals	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S ₂	58.6	58.3	4.3	4.1	15.2	15.6
7.	211	67.5	Colourless crystals	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	54.2	54.0	4.8	4.5	19.5	19.2
8.	300(d)	70.1	Dark brown crystals	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	52.3	52.1	4.5	4.3	16.7	16.4
9.	250(d)	51.8	Light brown leaflets	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ I	45.2	44.9	2.9	2.7	12.3	12.5
10.	210	75.2	Light brown crystals	C ₁₉ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ I ₂	28.4	28.0	1.8	1.6	11.2	11.5
11.	300(d)	94.2	Pinkish white crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	58.7	58.5	4.5	4.0	17.7	17.3
12.	267(d)	70.0	Brown crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S ₂	56.4	56.1	3.7	3.9	16.4	16.6
13.	289	70.1	Colourless leaflets	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	52.1	52.3	3.4	3.1	16.1	16.4
14.	210	38.0	Pinkish white needles	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	60.5	60.2	4.5	4.3	10.6	10.7
15.	236	52.6	Light brown prisms	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ SI	42.4	42.1	2.8	2.6	7.7	7.5
16.	238	66.4	Greyish white crystals	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	68.5	68.2	4.6	4.3	8.0	8.3
17.	245	53.1	Yellow prisms	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	67.9	68.2	4.5	4.3	8.0	8.3

'd' denotes decomposition.

* As recorded in Table I.

** Crystallised from ethanol, absolute ethanol or acetone.

2-Amino 6-naphthalene sulphonamidothiazole: To 2-aminothiazole (3 g.; 0.03 mol) in a round bottomed flask dry pyridine (5 ml) was added followed by the gradual addition of 2-acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride during 15 mins. and the contents stirred. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 5hr. in an oil bath at 75–85°; on cooling the product was transferred to a beaker containing ice-cold water (40 ml) and hydrochloric acid (7 ml). The deposited solid was filtered under suction, washed with cold water and dried; on crystallisation from hot glacial acetic acid, pure *2-acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonamidothiazole* was obtained in colourless crystals which decomposed at 300°. (Yield: 3.5 g; 33.6%).

The above acetyl derivative (2 g.) was refluxed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (20 ml; 15%) for 30 mins.; the cold solution was diluted with water and neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated product was filtered under suction, washed with water and dried; pure *2-amino-6-naphthalene sulphonamidothiazole* was crystallised from absolute ethanol in colourless needles which decomposed at 300°. (Yield : 0.8 g; 57%). (Found : C, 51.3; H, 3.7; S, 21.3. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_3S_2$; requires C, 51.1; H, 3.5; S, 21.0%).

2-Amino-6-naphthalene sulphonamidopyridine : In a round bottom flask fitted with a reflux condenser was placed 2-aminopyridine (5.6 g.; 0.06 mol), dry acetone (50 ml) and dry pyridine (3 ml) and 2-acetamido naphthalene 6-sulphonyl chloride (8.5 g; 0.03 mol) was gradually added with continuous stirring during 15 mins. The contents after heating on a water bath for 30 mins at 30–40° were left overnight and poured into the cold water (100 ml) containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml). The pink coloured deposited solid was filtered under suction, washed with cold water and dried; on crystallisation from ethanol pure *2-acetamido-6-naphthalene sulphonamidopyridine* was obtained as pinkish-white needles, m.p. 235°. (Yield : 4.8 g.; 46.8%).

The above product (3 g.) was deacetylated by refluxing with aqueous sodium hydroxide (20 ml; 15%) and subsequent neutralisation with dilute hydrochloric acid gave the free amino compound; on crystallisation with absolute ethanol pure *2-amino-6-naphthalene sulphonamidopyridine* was obtained as pinkish-white needles, m.p. 210°. (Yield : 1.0 g.; 38%). (Found : C, 60.5; H, 4.5; S, 10.6. $C_{15}H_{13}O_2N_3S$; requires C, 60.2; H, 4.3; S, 10.7%).

Department of Chemistry,
M.G. Science Institute,
Ahmedabad-9;
University of Delhi,
Delhi-7;
D.A.V. College,
Kanpur.

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